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● A new provincial record of *Trachystolodes huangjianbini* Huang, Guo & Liu (Cerambycidae) from Jiangxi Province

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Abstract: *Trachystolodes huangjianbini* Huang, Guo & Liu, 2020 was newly found from South Wudang Mountain of Jiangxi Province, China in June, 2024. It is the first record of this species outside of the type locality in Fujian Province. This species is characterized by the developed pronotal calluses, a pair of mushroom-shaped or ginkgo-shaped black setal spots on elytra, the femora and tibiae without golden hairs.

Keywords: China, longicorn beetles, morphology, new record, taxonomy

● 江西省天牛科一省级新记录种——黄剑斌糙天牛

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摘要: 2024年6月, 中国江西省南武当山新发现黄剑斌糙天牛 *Trachystolodes huangjianbini* Huang, Guo & Liu, 2020。这是该种在福建省模式产地之外的首次记录。本种具有以下特征: 前胸背板具发达的瘤突, 鞘翅上有一对蘑菇或银杏叶状的黑色斑, 腿节与胫节不具金黄色毛。

关键词: 中国, 天牛, 形态学, 新记录, 分类学

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Introduction

The genus *Trachystolodes* Breuning, 1943 belonging to the tribe Lamiini was established by Breuning (1943) for *Trachystola bimaculata* Kriesche, 1924. A total of five species were assigned to this genus, among which three species are endemic to southern China, one species is endemic to northern Vietnam, and only one species is widely distributed in southern China, Laos and Vietnam (Huang *et al.* 2020; Wang *et al.* 2021; Wang & He 2021).

During a diversity survey of forest pests in South Wudang Mountain of Jiangxi in June, 2024, the authors collect a female adult of *Trachystolodes*. After checking the morphological characteristics, the specimen was identified as *Trachystolodes huangjianbini* Huang, Guo & Liu, 2020. Hence, we decide to report and illustrate this interesting provincial record in this paper.

Material and methods

Specimens examined in this study were deposited in the Insect Collection of Forest Entomology Laboratory, Beijing Forestry University, Beijing, China (CBFU). Labels of the specimen are cited verbatim. Detail information of each label is listed in quotation marks (“”). Individual labels are separated by double slashes (/). Authors’ notes are in bracket ([]). The habitus photographs were taken using a Nikon D7100 camera with Laowa CF 60 mm f/2.8 2X Super Macro lens. For each final image, several photographs were taken at different focal planes and combined with Zerene Stacker to get one synthesized photograph. The distribution map was made with QGIS 3.28. All images were finally modified and arranged to plate by Adobe Photoshop CC 2019.

Taxonomy

Checklist of the genus *Trachystolodes* Breuning, 1943 糙天牛属

1. *T. bimaculatus* (Kriesche, 1924) 糙天牛: VIETNAM
2. *T. tonkinensis* Breuning, 1943 双斑糙天牛: CHINA (Fujian, Jiangxi, Guangdong, Hainan, Guangxi, Guizhou, Sichuan, Yunnan); VIETNAM; LAOS
3. *T. huangjianbini* Huang, Guo & Liu, 2020 黄剑斌糙天牛: CHINA (Fujian, Jiangxi (**new provincial record**))
4. *T. tianjialini* Wang, Xie & Wang, 2021 田家麟糙天牛: CHINA (Hubei)
5. *T. neltharion* Wang & He, 2021 死亡之翼糙天牛: CHINA (Yunnan)

Trachystolodes huangjianbini Huang, Guo & Liu, 2020 黄剑斌糙天牛

Figs 1A–C

Huang *et al.* 2020: 52, figs 5–28, 52 (description; illustrations).

Type locality: “CHINA: Fujian. Mountain temple, Gaoping village, Mangdang mountain, Nanping city, 118°5’24” E, 26°37’43” N, alt. 923 m”.

Material examined. 1♀ (CBFU), “CHINA, Jiangxi: Ganzhou City, Longnan, South Wudang Mountain” [in Chinese] // “alt.800m, 2024.VI-2, Jun Ding leg.”.

Distribution. China: Nanping and Sanming cities of Fujian Province (original records); Ganzhou City of Jiangxi Province (**new provincial record**).

Remarks. This species was stenochoric and only found from central Fujian according to the origin paper. However, the new record herein is located in the south Jiangxi adjoining Guangdong, more than 350 km from the type locality across Wuyi Mountains. It could mean that the distribution range of *T. huangjianbini* may be more widespread than previous thought.

FIGURE 1. *Trachystolodes huangjianbini* Huang, Guo & Liu, 2020, ♀, Jiangxi: A habitus, dorsal view B pronotum, dorsal view C head, frontal view.

FIGURE 2. *Trachystolodes* species: A distribution from eastern China (excluding *T. tonkinensis* Breuning, 1943), green: *T. tianjialini*, yellow: *T. huangjianbini* B habitat of *T. huangjianbini* from Jiangxi.

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Additional information

Author contributions: Conceptualization, Resources, Visualization: J Ding; Writing—original draft and editing: J-H Chen; Writing—review: X-R Yang.

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